

Complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) with 2-Substituted-3-amino-quinazoline-4-ones : A Physico-chemical Study

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Complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) with 2-methyl-3-amino-quinazoline-4-one (MAQ) and 2-phenyl-3-amino-quinazoline-4-one (PAQ) have been prepared and characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, magnetic moment, conductivity, thermal, infrared, electronic and nmr spectral data. The stoichiometry of the complexes is found to be $[\text{CuL}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$, $[\text{NiL}_2 \cdot \text{Cl}_2]$, $[\text{CoL}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2]$, $[\text{ZnL}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2]$ and $[\text{CdL}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2]$ (L=MAQ or PAQ). Infrared spectral data indicate that both the ligands act as bidentate ones coordinating through amino nitrogen and oxygen of amido carbonyl group in all the complexes. Based on electronic spectra and the other data, the geometry of the complexes has been assigned; Cu(II), Co(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) complexes are tetrahedral whereas the Ni(II) complex is octahedral.

ORGANIC ligands having nitrogen, oxygen and sulphur as donor atoms have been the subject of much current research. Quinazoline-2-thione-4-one was shown to behave in different ways, in some complexes acting as monodentate ligand with sulphur or oxygen as the coordinating atom and in some others as bidentate, coordinating through sulphur and tertiary nitrogen¹. 2-Substituted-3-amino-

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R=OH, Ph.

quinazoline-4-ones (I) possess various coordinating sites similar to quinazoline-2-thione-4-one and is expected to form complexes with different metal ions. Therefore, it was thought worthwhile to make a study of the complexing behaviour of these ligands. The present paper deals with the preparation of the complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) with 2-methyl-3-amino-quinazoline-4-one (MAQ) and 2-phenyl-3-amino-quinazoline-4-one (PAQ) and their characterization based on various physico-chemical data.

Experimental

All reagents used in the present work were of A.R. grade. The ligands were prepared as reported in the literature².

Co(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) complexes were prepared using metal acetates and Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes using $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, respectively. The following general procedure was adopted. The metal salt was dissolved in methanol. Methanolic ligand solution in slight excess over the 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) ratio was added to it dropwise with constant stirring. The complex formed immediately after refluxing the reaction mixture for 30 min on water bath. It was filtered, washed several times with hot water and then with methanol until free from the reagent. The complex was dried in vacuum over anhydrous calcium chloride.

The analytical data (C, H, N) for the complexes were obtained from micro-analytical laboratory, University of Calcutta, Calcutta. The metal content of the complexes was determined by standard procedures. The magnetic susceptibility measurements were made at room temperature by Guoy method using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as the calibrant. Diamagnetic corrections were applied using Pascal's constants. The thermograms of the complexes were recorded using a Stanton recording thermobalance, model HI-5M. The infrared spectra of the ligands and the complexes in nujol ($4000\text{-}200\text{ cm}^{-1}$) were recorded on Perkin Elmer Infrared spectrophotometer, Model-283, and electronic spectra in DMF on Shimadzu Multipurpose Recording Spectrophotometer, Model-MPS-5000. The conductance measurements were made in DMF with Systronics conductivity bridge, Model-305. 100 MHz ^1H nmr spectra of the ligands and their Zn(II) complexes in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ were recorded on Jeol instrument. The spectra of Cd(II) complexes could not be recorded for want of sufficient solubility.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analyses of the complexes (Table 1) indicate that their composition may be represented as $[\text{CuL}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$, $[\text{NiL}_2 \cdot \text{Cl}_2]$, $[\text{CoL}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2]$, $[\text{ZnL}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2]$ and $[\text{CdL}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2]$ (L = MAQ or PAQ). All the complexes are stable at room temperature and are non-hygroscopic. They decompose at higher ($>300^\circ$) temperatures. The complexes are insoluble in water and many of the common organic solvents, but appreciably soluble in DMF.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPOUNDS

Compound	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)			
	M	C	N	H
MAQ	—	61.71 (61.32)	24.00 (23.88)	5.14 (4.98)
$[\text{Cu}(\text{MAQ})\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$	18.02 (17.88)	30.64 (30.12)	11.92 (12.25)	3.12 (3.02)
$[\text{Ni}(\text{MAQ})_2\text{Cl}_2]$	12.24 (12.04)	45.04 (44.82)	17.52 (17.25)	3.12 (3.02)
$[\text{Co}(\text{MAQ})(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2]$	17.23 (16.98)	45.62 (45.09)	12.21 (11.88)	4.39 (4.32)
$[\text{Zn}(\text{MAQ})(\text{OH}_2\text{COO})_2]$	18.76 (18.36)	44.77 (44.23)	12.06 (11.84)	4.30 (4.12)
$[\text{Cd}(\text{MAQ})(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2]$	28.43 (28.58)	30.45 (30.02)	10.62 (10.12)	3.79 (3.56)
PAQ	—	70.89 (70.12)	17.72 (17.58)	4.64 (4.33)
$[\text{Cu}(\text{PAQ})(\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O})]$	15.33 (15.68)	40.53 (40.12)	10.13 (9.89)	3.14 (3.66)
$[\text{Ni}(\text{PAQ})_2\text{Cl}_2]$	9.73 (9.12)	55.66 (55.08)	13.92 (13.78)	3.66 (3.88)
$[\text{Co}(\text{PAQ})(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2]$	14.59 (13.88)	53.48 (52.88)	10.40 (10.56)	4.21 (4.02)
$[\text{Zn}(\text{PAQ})(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2]$	15.93 (15.24)	52.64 (52.38)	10.23 (10.12)	4.14 (4.32)
$[\text{Cd}(\text{PAQ})(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2]$	24.57 (24.22)	47.22 (46.56)	9.18 (9.12)	3.72 (3.52)

The DMF solutions of the complexes at $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ show electrical conductances in the 5-20 $\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mole}^{-1}$ range, indicative of their non-ionic nature. The non electrolytic behaviour of the complexes implies that the anions are present inside the coordination sphere.

Thermal study: It is known from the thermogravimetric curves of the complexes that they are

thermally stable to varying degree. The thermograms of Cu(II) complexes each show weight loss at 160° which corresponds to one water molecule. The loss of water at this temperature indicates that it is coordinated to the metal ions³. The thermograms of all the complexes show two common transformation steps, the first one in the $300-400^\circ$ range corresponding to the loss of ligand moiety and the second one in the $400-600^\circ$ range corresponding to the loss of anions. The final products of decomposition of the complexes correspond, in each case, to metallic oxide.

Infrared spectra: Some important infrared absorption frequencies of the ligands and the complexes and their assignments are given in Table 2.

Both the ligands show two sharp bands around 3360 and 3100 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of NH_2 group, respectively⁴. The lower shift of the asymmetric stretching band in the spectra of all the complexes indicates the participation of NH_2 in the metal-ligand bond. Further, the ligands display a band at 1580 cm^{-1} due to NH_2 deformation. This undergoes higher shift by $20-40\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes which supports the involvement of the NH_2 group in bonding⁵. $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ vibration which appears in the $1680-1660\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region in the ligands is shifted by $20-30\text{ cm}^{-1}$ towards lower region in the complexes. This indicates that the oxygen of this group is also coordinating. The fact that the nitrogen of NH_2 group and oxygen of $\text{C}=\text{O}$ group are coordinating is further evidenced by the presence of $\nu\text{M}-\text{N}$ and $\nu\text{M}-\text{O}$ bands around 500 and 475 cm^{-1} , respectively in the far infrared region of the metal complexes⁶.

In addition to these, the ir spectra of Cu(II) complexes show a band in the $3500-3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region indicating the presence of water. The appearance of one more band at 695 cm^{-1} suggests that it is present in the coordination sphere. Further, the spectra exhibit broad SO_4^{2-} vibrations at 1140 and 1090 cm^{-1} (ν_3 split) and 940 cm^{-1} (ν_1) indicating that SO_4^{2-} group is coordinating⁷.

A band observed at 280 cm^{-1} in Ni(II) complexes has been attributed to $\nu\text{Ni}-\text{Cl}^8$.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPOUNDS

Compound	Infrared bands cm^{-1}				$\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$	μ_{eff} B.M.
	$\nu_2\text{NH}_2$	$\nu_1\text{NH}_2$	δNH_2	$\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$			
MAQ	3340	3100	1580	1660	—	—	—
$[\text{Cu}(\text{MAQ})\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$	3290	3070	1620	1640	475	505	2.15
$[\text{Ni}(\text{MAQ})_2\text{Cl}_2]$	3285	3065	1605	1630	480	495	3.20
$[\text{Co}(\text{MAQ})(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2]$	3280	3060	1600	1635	485	500	4.30
$[\text{Zn}(\text{MAQ})(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2]$	3290	3065	1610	1645	475	510	—
$[\text{Cd}(\text{MAQ})(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2]$	3285	3065	1610	1640	475	500	—
PAQ	3360	3120	1580	1670	—	—	—
$[\text{Cu}(\text{PAQ})(\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O})]$	3290	3085	1615	1650	475	510	2.20
$[\text{Ni}(\text{PAQ})_2\text{Cl}_2]$	3280	3090	1605	1645	470	495	3.28
$[\text{Co}(\text{PAQ})(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2]$	3275	3030	1600	1640	485	500	4.35
$[\text{Zn}(\text{PAQ})(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2]$	3300	3075	1615	1640	480	505	—
$[\text{Cd}(\text{PAQ})(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2]$	3300	3080	1615	1645	475	500	—

In the case of Co(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) complexes, the bands at 1440 and 1340 cm^{-1} have been assigned to $\nu(\text{COO})$ and $\delta(\text{CH}_3)$ vibrations indicating the coordination of acetate ion to the metal ions⁹.

Magnetic moment and electronic spectra: The magnetic moment values of the complexes are listed in Table 2.

Cu(II) complexes with MAQ and PAQ have magnetic moment values of 2.15 and 2.20 B.M., respectively. Cu(II) complexes, irrespective of the stereochemistry, possess magnetic moment equivalent to one unpaired electron, but orbital angular momentum makes an additional contribution to a different degree in different geometries. Large orbital contribution to magnetic moment has been used as an evidence for tetrahedral Cu(II) complexes^{10,11}. The large values obtained for the present Cu(II) complexes suggest tetrahedral orientation of the ligands around Cu(II).

The electronic spectra of Cu(II) complexes show two peaks around 13080 and 25000 cm^{-1} . For a tetrahedral Cu(II) complex, crystal field theory predicts only one transition ${}^2T_2 \rightarrow {}^2E$ which occurs below 10000 cm^{-1} . However, Sacconi and Ciampolini, studying the electronic spectra of salicylidene-aminato Cu(II) complexes, reported that flattening of the tetrahedral geometry results in the splitting of both ground and excited levels giving rise to four transitions. They, however, obtained only three peaks at 8500, 13600 and 21000 cm^{-1} and assigned a pseudo tetrahedral geometry. The higher energy peaks observed in the present Cu(II) complexes may, therefore, be assigned, in conformity with the earlier observations^{12,13}, to a pseudo tetrahedral configuration.

Ni(II) complexes are shown to be paramagnetic, the μ_{eff} being 3.20 and 3.28 B.M. It has been reported that octahedral Ni(II) complexes exhibit the values in the 2.9-3.3 B.M. range whereas in tetrahedral complexes the moments are as high as 4.1 B.M.¹⁴. The values obtained for the present complexes favour an octahedral environment.

Further, the electronic spectra of Ni(II) complexes reveal three peaks at 8900, 14800 and 25200 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to ${}^3A_{2g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(\text{F})$, ${}^3A_{2g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(\text{F})$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(\text{P})$ transitions, respectively. These data together with the magnetic moment values are suggestive of an octahedral geometry for the complexes¹⁵.

Co(II) complexes show magnetic moment values of 4.30 and 4.36 B.M. The tetrahedral Co(II) complexes have generally lower values of magnetic moment (4.2-4.7 B.M.) as compared to octahedral Co(II) complexes (4.7-5.6 B.M.)¹⁶. The values obtained in the present investigation suggest a tetrahedral structure. Further, the electronic spectra of these complexes show a band at 15380 cm^{-1} due to ${}^4A_2(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4T_1(\text{P})$ and the absence of any band

around 22220 cm^{-1} further corroborates the tetrahedral geometry for the complexes¹⁷.

Zn(II) and Cd(II) complexes are found to be diamagnetic.

NMR spectra: The ${}^1\text{H}$ nmr spectra of the ligands show signals at 7.1 to 8.8 δ which are due to aromatic protons¹⁸. A signal at 2.46 δ in the spectrum of MAQ has been assigned to methyl protons. Integrated intensities obtained are in good agreement with the number of different kinds of protons present in the ligands. In addition, both the ligands give rise to a signal at 6.4 δ due to NH_2 moiety. In the complexes this signal undergoes a downward shift as 8.1 δ , indicating the participation of amino nitrogen in coordination.

Tetrahedral geometry is the most preferred structure for the tetracoordinated Zn(II) and Cd(II) complexes¹⁹. On the basis of elemental analysis, conductance, infrared and nmr spectral data, tetrahedral geometry is proposed for Zn(II) and Cd(II) complexes.

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